

Defect studies on chemically synthesized FeCo by positron lifetime spectroscopy

P. Rajesh¹, S. Sellaiyan², A. Uedono², T. Arun³, R. Justin Joseyphus^{1,*}

¹Magnetic Materials Laboratory, Department of Physics, National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, 620015.

²Division of Applied Physics, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan 305-8571.

³Advanced Materials Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.

*rjustinj@nitt.edu

Abstract

FeCo alloys exhibit B2 type ordered and A2 type disordered structure whose magnetic and mechanical properties are different. Positron lifetime spectroscopy (PAS) was undertaken for the chemically synthesized FeCo samples and compared with Fe, Co and annealed FeCo. PAS of the asprepared sample resulted in two short lived lifetime components and two long lived lifetime components in the ns region. The shorter lifetime components are attributed to the interfaces and cluster vacancies respectively. The longer lifetime components originate from pick-off annihilation of orthopositronium (o-Ps) in the small and large voids and its annihilation at larger voids due to the flower like morphology. The disordered FeCo transforms to the ordered form on annealing at 700 °C. The studies suggest that FeCo alloys synthesized through chemical methods could also produce porous structure with properties different from the bulk.

Keywords: Positron annihilation, magnetic nanoparticles, soft magnetic materials